
TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE MANAGEMENT IN RURAL AND URBAN COMMUNITIES IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

Musiliu Iyanda Kareem

Centre for Environmental Studies and Sustainable Development (CESSSED),
Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos.

Rotimi Williams Olatunji

School of Communication,
Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos.

ABSTRACT

Environmental noise continues to create major health hazard especially in our urban communities and the environment is fast deteriorating. Lagos is already experiencing the ill effects of environmental noise on many fronts with numerous challenges. This study evaluated challenges associated with environmental noise in rural and urban communities in Lagos and the potential solution towards attaining sustainable green environment. Without a healthy society, since it has been established in various studies that there exist connection between environment and health, sustainability achievement will be difficulty. Purposive and cluster sampling technique were adopted to select the study areas, with 400 respondents selected. Self-designed questionnaire was administered which were subjected to reliability test with the test retest method of 0.85co-efficient. The hypothesis was tested using independent sample t-test. The study shows that the challenges associated with environmental noise in rural and urban communities in Lagos is statistically significant an indication that environment noise is a clog in the wheel of achieving sustainable green environment. Grounded on the intensity and knowledge of health impacts of environmental noise, the study recommended that government should urgently embark on reconstruction and retooling of educational approaches towards environmental challenges and impacts as to enthrone clean and friendly environment that will promote healthy living.

Key words: Environment Noise, Green Environment, Sustainable, Perception, Challenges

Introduction

One of the persistent environmental issues today is high environmental noise levels in residential areas especially in the urban communities. Environmental noise is regarded as silent killers which have been for long forgotten but now taken its tools on the nation. Robert (1910) predicted that environmental noise will be the epidemic of the future and mankind will have to fight it as relentlessly as the plague and cholera. With the rapid spread and endemic situation of environmental noise today Robert assertion cannot be rejected. Along this line World Wildlife Fund (WWF, 2016) said that accumulated evidences indicates that the actions and habits of a single species, Homo-sapiens is leading to the planet's unprecedented dysfunction. That is the scale and pace of biodiversity loss are attributed to human activities in which environmental noise cannot be alienated.

Environment in the contemporary context is seen by Akinbode (2002) as the totality of the places and the surroundings, in which we live, work and interact with other people in our cultural, religious, political, and socio-economic activities for self-fulfillment and the advancement of our communities, societies, and nations. Enda, Murphy, Eoin (2014) stated that environmental noise is unwanted sound created by human activities that is considered harmful and detrimental to human health and quality of life.

Probing on the impacts Sadorsky (2014) added that the important resources like air, water, and soil have been contaminated by the release of toxic substances on one hand and the other; development activities also make the lives of the people miserable through nuisance and one of such nuisance is the generation of higher sound levels, which our ear is unable to bear.

Kirkegaard and Gisladdottir (2016) conclude that environmental noise in cities has long been recognized as a threat to the quality of life and well-being due to its harmful effects.

All these empirical studies point to the fact that environment is the most valuable asset that we own, share and use together with other people for the mutual benefits of society which must be protected.

In the recent time environmental noise has become one of the most important environmental stressors affecting public health throughout the world. As the days arises and increase in economic growth, social advancement and technological development, environmental noise level increases around home and work places, with adverse effects on people's health. This has led to additional concern about this kind of pollution with little efforts. On this Rumberg (2009) opined that the action to reduce environmental noise has had a very lower priority than that embark upon to address other environmental problems, such as air and water pollution.

Various research work in recent years point to the fact that environmental noise has received considerable worldwide attention as a result of many studies linking environmental noise to various health effects (Basner, Babisch, Davis, Brink & Clark, 2014; Buket, Elif & Oner, 2017; Chen, Ni, Zhang, Kong & Lu, 2017; Munzel et al., 2017; Munzel, Schmidt, Steven, Herzog, Daiber, & Sorensen, 2018) all the researchers in their findings concluded that environmental noise has various effects on human health. Studies have revealed that it is high time for sustainable steps to be taken in an effort to stop or reduce the effects and restore healthy environment for all the people.

Reducing environmental noise in the built environment also aligns with some of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, especially Goals 3 (which stated that "ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages"). And ii ("make cities and human settlements

inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable”). But the SDG failed to accord environmental noise the right place in its goals with various evidences that environmental noise is a global problem that continues to undermine sustainable environment.

With details knowledge of environmental noise, it shows that environmental noise issue cut across all the SDGs goals, so failure to include environmental noise as a consideration in deliberation on sustainable green environment may threaten the overall success. At the same time more determinations are require towards the realization of the objectives of sustainable green environment that will usher in a healthy environment.

The impact of environmental noise on human health that resulted from technological transformations which introduced innovative ways of working, living and transformed society particularly to cities and hastened the process that resulted in populations moving from rural to urban centers can be justified with the saying that environmental noise is the price to pay for the development. But this is no longer the case; society is now vocally insisting that industry whose technology has created most of the environmental noise should put back the problem to tolerable limit towards a green sustainability.

In Nigeria today, the city populations are growing faster than the infrastructure can adapt, residents in our big cities are going through the gradual process of partial deafness. Among the environmental noise; traffic noise is the greatest concern to the majority of people.

Anomohanran and Osemeikhian (2006) in their study found that causes of environmental noise especially in Nigeria include transport activities such as automobiles, commercial motorcycles, recording houses, use of electricity generators, and religious activities.

Ukonze et al, (2020) also identified traffic noise as major environmental noise disturbing residential areas resulting from worsening of the road system; air pollution, traffic congestion, and vehicle ownership in Nigeria which are now on a high scale.

But lack of knowledge about the harmful effects of environmental noise had contributed to non-appreciating the effects. Oyedepo (2013) opined that the control of environmental noise has been hampered by insufficient knowledge of its effects on humans and lack of defined criteria.

In a study conducted by Ayodeji and Olumuyiwa (2016) among the Students of Tertiary Institutions in Ilesa, on Awareness and Self Perceived Effects of Noise, the study revealed that there was a moderate level of awareness of the effects of noise among the participants, 58.4% of the respondents. Peoples' conversation, generator, and traffic congestion were common sources of noise. Despite this level of awareness of noise, awareness of the existence of noise regulatory law is very low. Only 24% of the respondents were aware of the law.

In a similar study conducted by Firduas and Ahmad (2018) among the students in Delhi, it was discovered that the majority of educated youth is aware of noise, its causes, and probability health effects but the vast majority of educated youth did not perceive noise as an environmental challenge and ranked it as a least important threat to the health and environment. These infer that the majority of educated youth understand the health-related implications of environmental noise in Delhi. But research has noted that information alone cannot change behavior, other key critical factors at play include environmental identities and values, attitudes and motivation according to Kollmus and Agyeman, 2002, Gatersleben,

Murtagh and Abrahamse, 2014, even action to take and how on effects of environmental noise is vital.

Examining the challenge to effective environmental noise control, it appears that a huge gap exist in the legal, institutional and management standards in the country. Oyedepo (2012) pointed out that there is no legal framework on which noise can be abated in Nigeria and her citizenry are yet to come to terms with the present and future impacts of environmental noise on the environment. This denotes that environmental noise control and management is still weak in Nigeria which contributed to the challenges facing the country. On the basis of this Ijaiya, (2014) concluded that in Nigeria, environmental noise control is yet to receive the full attention it deserves in this part of the world. It further signifies that few laws and regulatory provision on environmental noise in Nigeria is totally detached from the aims due to lack of proper implementation. The most unfortunate regarding environmental noise challenges hinges on the main actor nonchalant attitude or showing of little understanding on the impact of environmental noise on the present and future environment. Environmental noise reduction is one of the fundamental developments toward green sustainability. Even the policymakers designing the environmental noise policies try in motivating behavior changes in people; but the people may on the other hand fail to change to more sustainable practices, though tending to defeat the effectiveness of environmental noise policies. Recent research on sustainable behavior among homeowners suggests that even when people are environmentally educated and willing to act sustainably, they may still fail to adapt their behavior because they anticipate inconveniences and experience other psychological barriers to changing their behavior (De Vries, Rietkerk, & Kooger, 2019).

In studying the challenges and surveying means of reducing, which might assist the policymakers to achieve the set behavioural goals in environmental noise agreements, it is necessary to design a strategic policy to raise awareness on environmental noise issues with a clearly defined goals calling for action and at the same time illustrating how the various issues can be tackled. In the recent, environmental noise is gaining momentum as a key policy area and was fully put on the agenda as a sustainability issue, hence the extent of its detriment to the environment was accepted (DEFRA, 2001). In line with this, Baer and Reuter (2015) emphasis the need to include perspectives from different sectors and disciplines when considering formulating and implementing new policies and programs.

Sustainable Green Environment

In the recent, the concept of sustainability has been getting globalattention from public sector, academics and practitioners. Sustainable Green Environment has to do with act of exhibiting deliberate concerns for environmental conservation and also improved health of the environment. Going green is a way of living one's life in a more sustainable way and making sure that one's activities as individuals or in a community does not have negative impacts on resources in the environment.

Sustainable development on the other hand has been define in many ways by different studies, but the most frequently quoted definition is from Our Common Future, known as the Brundtland Report. Sustainable development is defined as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (UN, 1987). The World Business Council (1997) further offered that "sustainable development involves the simultaneous pursuit of economic prosperity, environmental quality and social equity." These three pillars, economic, environmental, and social, align with Elkington's triple bottom line (TBL) of profit, planet, and people (John,

1994). Sustainable development is a socio-economic and political movement with global appeal, which focus on environmental protection and economic development that would make life more pleasant to the people on earth.

The United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) describe the major development challenges to these pursuits. Adopted by 193 countries in 2015, the SDGs are known officially as the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN, 2015). These SDGs describe the major development challenges facing humanity and serve as a roadmap to address some of the world's biggest challenges today. Though SDGs stated all the major development challenges facing humanity and define way to address some of the biggest challenges today. But Scharlemann et al.,(2020) regarded the envisioned as an “indivisible whole,” as the goals and targets relate to and depend on each other. Kihlman (2006) advance that with evidence pointing to adverse health impacts, in discussions regarding the environment and sustainable development, the issue of noise is often neglected. It is very clear that issue of environmental noise and its many impacts on sustainable development are not given much attention.

In fact with the well-established interconnected links of environmental noise to adverse economic, social and environmental development, environmental noise was not feature as a target in any of the 17 goals any of the 169 associated targets of SDGs. King (2022) argues that good sound management, alongside noise control, can assist in the realization of some of the SDGs goals.

The transformation toward environmental noise for sustainable green environment required integration approaches that will bring together multiple stakeholders around to share objectives.

According to OECD (2010) sustainable strategies are usually based “on the identification and evaluation of criteria that expose potential impacts on the three dimensions of sustainable development, namely, social, economic and environment. Such tactics must promote an all- inclusive end-to-end analysis of different dimensions, which must incorporate vulnerability risks and environmental impacts.

Challenges are abound in advancing environmental noise in rural and urban areas and overcoming them is essential if we are to achieve sustainable green environment. To meet the demands for green skills for the environment, engagement in the areas of education, transportation and reorientation is very vital. This made Kopnina (2017) note that without an understanding of concrete barriers, the challenge of addressing unsustainable practices becomes insurmountable.

Education and Reorientation

Education is very vital for attaining a green environment. Education enables us to understand ourselves and other and our links with the wider natural and social environment (Elaine, 2008).

Education process serves to change the attitudes and orientation of individual. Lack of improvement in education will not enhance innovation, knowledge sharing and awareness about the varieties of environmental noise issues and the public health implications. It is necessary to pursue knowledge and practices which can lead to more environmentally friendly and ecologically dependable decisions and lifestyles that will help to safeguard the environment and sustain its natural resources for the present and future generation. It should

be noted that good quality education is an indispensable tool for accomplishing a sustainable world. Education being an instrument of systematic change is fundamental if we are to successfully modify man's conception about nature and adjust attitudes to the sustainable environment.

An education system that focus on how the systems can best provide the people with the skills, values, attitudes and behavior that will empower them care for their environment. That is the reason which made Denen (2020) believes that adopting the educational approach to the development of value reorientation will serve as best way to ensure growth and development.

Furthermore, the issue of serious reorientation on the attitudes towards environmental problems is another angle to achieving sustainable green environment. Re-orientation itself is a rehabilitated orientation that has to do with a changed in set of attitudes and beliefs, the action of thinking over our stand in a relationship to our environment and adjusting our tract. Asobie, (2012) explain that it is a transformation on a fundamental shift in the deep orientation of a person, an organization, or a society such that the world is seen in new ways, new actions and results which become possible that were impossible prior to the transformation. But Njoku (2011) sees value reorientation as inculcating good values that can help Nigeria out of her numerous predicaments and can refocus the nation through greatness. Critical analysis of this definition show that a society can be rapidly transformed if able to embraces good moral values that have the potentials to re-orientate the attitude and behaviours of the citizens.

The use of green energy might not be achieved if the reorientations to adopt using energy safer are not built. Most rural residents do not have access to electricity, even our urban areas are ranked among the lowest in electricity access rates. The inefficiency in energy can be attributed to lack of incentives, poor regulatory framework, lack of enforceable policy and inadequate infrastructure. It is by understanding the scale and the nature of environmental noise problem with impact on sustainability that policies can be formulated and implemented which will support the mitigation of environmental noise and protect areas of good quality. So without government investment in the energy sector then achieving sustainable green environment will be a mirage.

Transport is another major contributor to environmental noise problem. Promoting and supporting a transport system that is environmental-friendly aimed at reducing traffic congestion and deemphasizing reliance on private transportation, will be a tool to attain sustainable green environment. Alves, et al.(2018) concluded that reduction of environmental impact has been considered as one of the key principle for governments and society.

Environmental Noise in Lagos State

In Lagos State environmental noise continues to attract more public complaints over the years, more than any other single environmental subject. People sensitive eardrums are daily being bombarded by a continuous barraged of environmental noise overflowing from ear-shattering, drum-size, speakers of mosques and churches, hammering neighbour's musical system, harsh horns of motorists, piercing sirens of escorts, thunderous weekend open parties and worse now, from high-pitched explosions of numerous record and cassette selling kiosks. To find solution to this nasty experience, Fagbohun (2011) advanced that the very nature of environmental concerns, their complexity, the necessary holistic solutions, the need to respond to changing circumstances, and the high degree of uncertainty necessitate that appropriate policy is developed to meet the challenges.

In recent time, in line with Fagbohun (2011) suggestion, it appears that Lagos State policy direction is now looking to examine and address the spectrum of pollution more holistically, as articulated, in the new Environmental Management and Protection Law in 2017, thus bringing all existing related environmental laws with the sole aim of achieving clean and smart environment for Lagos State. This paper recognizes that Lagos State population is growing at a fast rate and yet enough attention has not been placed on the role of environmental noise in sustainable green environment. The environmental situation in Lagos State is increasingly being polluted with varied negative health effects, as it constitutes a major threat to attaining sustainable green environment.

Statement of the Problem

Most previous studies either focused on environmental issues separately or merely interrogated environmental noise measurement distinctively. Studies on environmental noise have been carried out in Nigeria especially in Lagos but there is a dearth of research in this area, Adegboyega (2018) emphasized on generation of noise in urban areas of Nigeria especially Lagos. The present study examines challenges associated with environmental noise in rural and urban communities of Lagos State as well as solution towards achieving sustainable green environment. An attempt to fill this gap prompted the conduct of this study with a focus on Lagos State which is very well known for environmental noise as a result of its mega city status with high level of industrial and commercial activities.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to examine challenges associated with environmental noise in rural and urban communities in Lagos with possible solution towards attaining sustainable green environment. The relevance of this study based on the fact that environmental noise has a vital role to play in achieving sustainable green environment both in rural and urban areas, and not only in urban areas where most attention is focused at the expense of rural areas. Based on this broad objective, this study hypothesized that, “There will be no statistically significant difference in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise between the residents of rural and urban communities in Lagos State”.

Research Design, Methods and Materials

The study adopted descriptive survey research design (i.e. quantitative) to obtain primary data through questionnaire. This enables evidence to be obtained from the sampled population. Lagos State is recognized as most urbanized and facing environmental noise problems as a result of its mega city status with high level of industrial and commercial activities. There are twenty local governments’ areas in the state in which the study addresses two of them. The two clusters local government includes Ikeja referred to as urban and Badagry as rural were selected using simple random sampling.

This study was specifically carried out in five areas selected within the local government as follows: Pepple Street, Allen Junction/Kudirat Abiola Way, Onigbongbo, Obafemi Awolowo Road, and ACME Road in Ikeja Local Government Area of Lagos State (all urban locations). In addition, for the rural areas, Ibereko, Badagry Market, Mowo/Pota/Ikoga, Ajara Round about, and Oko Afo/Ilogbo Eremi in Badagry Local Government Area were selected. The target groups were selected using the purposive sampling method. For the questionnaire respondents, a total of 400 residents were sampled. Forty respondents were selected from each area making a total of 400 respondents. Cluster sampling method was used to select cluster communities experiencing environmental noise in selected local government areas.

The self-report questionnaire titled “The perception about challenges associated with environmental noise in rural and urban communities in Lagos State” was employed for the study. It was validated and subjected to reliability of test retest method at 0.85 co-efficient. The study consisted of two parts, Section A help to generate information on demographic and section B was used to generate information from the designed research objective. The questionnaire was constructed in five Likert scales for the items in the following manner- Always (A), Usually (U), Neutral (N), Occasionally (O), Never (N). Ethical procedures include the fact that the researchers guaranteed a high degree of anonymity for the respondents who were also assured that participation was voluntary.

The questionnaire was administered on the respondents to fill and the entire questionnaire were duly filled and returned. For data collection purposes, five people were responsible for the collection of questionnaire from the respondents. This consists of the researcher who was assisted by four trained research assistants. Respondents of residents to questionnaire were coded into the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23. Data were analyzed using independent t-test.

Results

Test of Hypothesis

H₀: There is no statistically significant difference in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise between the residents of rural and urban communities in Lagos State.

**Table 1: Result of the Independent Sample t-test for Hypothesis
 Sample Size: 400 Respondents**

Group Statistics:	
Mean responses for Urban	2.834
Mean responses for Rural	2.543
Mean Difference	0.291
Standard Deviation – Urban	0.515
Standard Deviation – Rural	0.638
Leven’s Test for Equality of Variances:	
F	8.841
p-value	0.003
Independent t-test – Equal Variances Assumed (student t-test):	
t-statistic	4.950
p-value	0.000
95% confidence interval of the mean difference	Lower: 0.176 Upper: 0.407
Independent t-test – Equal Variances Not Assumed (Welch’s t-test):	
t-statistic	4.646
p-value	0.000
95% confidence interval of the mean difference	Lower: 0.168 Upper: 0.415
Effect Size (Eta Squared):	
	0.051

Source: Author’s computation, 2024.

Table 1 presents the result of the independent-sample t-test for the hypothesis. The Leven’s test for the equality (homogeneity) of variance is ($F = 8.841$, $p\text{-value} = 0.003 < 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis of equal variance cannot be accepted. More evidently, the boxplot (figure 1) shows the degree of the variability in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise in the rural and urban communities.

Figure1: Box plot for the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise.

As shown in figure 1 Welch’s t -test is considered suitable for the test of this hypothesis. The Welch’s t -test for unequal variance test ($t(238.026) = 4.646$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$) reveals that there is a statistically significant difference in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise between the residents of rural community ($Mean = 2.543$, $SD = 0.638$) and urban community ($Mean = 2.834$, $SD = 0.515$) in Lagos State. The null hypothesis that “there is no statistically significant difference in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise between the residents of rural and urban communities in Lagos State” is rejected. The result implies that there is statistically significant difference in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise between the rural and urban communities in Lagos State. This is an indication that sustainable green environment could not be achieved in this situation in which the residents are not aware that environmental noise with its human impact play a significant role.

Discussion

Hypothesis of the study suggests that an equal variance in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise shows the degree of the variability in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise in the rural and urban communities. It can be observed that larger variability features obviously among the residents in the rural communities as compared with those in the urban communities.

Meanwhile, the effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.051$) suggests that about 5.1% of the total variance in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise is explained by the residents’ location (urban and rural). This effect size appears to be small. This implies that there are other dominant factors that determine the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise aside from the locations of the residents. The Welch’s t -test reveals that there is a statistically significant difference in the perception about challenges

associated with environmental noise between the residents of rural communities and urban communities in Lagos State. By implication, it means that this variability on perception about challenges associated with environmental noise clearly revealed that sustainable green development could only be achieved when the residents are aware of challenges associated with environmental noise and the impacts which will change their awareness behavior; this is possible through education and proper reorientation of the citizens.

The study revealed that differences in the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise, for instance, those in urban areas are perceived to be more prone to environmental noise than those in rural areas. Consequently, their perception towards these challenges made them leaves an event if the sound is too loud, report neighbour to the community; discuss environmental noise issues with neighbours, etc. The perception towards these challenges such as leaving event if the sound is too loud, report neighbour to the community and discuss environmental noise issues with neighbours as shown by study is a positive decision because actions of group will likely affect the achievement of the others, with this better understanding of the interactions among the residents toward environmental noise then consequence for achieving sustainable green environment will be limited. So identifying environmentally sound development will be an essential to meeting environmental noise challenges and also ensuring sustainable green environment.

On the government policies on environmental noise, it was observed from the result that rules and regulations are not heard which boil to the fact that residents were not aware of the law or their right as citizens and poor implementation of the law. The finding is in line with the study of Ayodeji and Olumuyiwa (2016) that indicate only 24% of the respondent were aware of the law.

Furthermore Fagbohun (2011) advanced that the very nature of environmental concerns, their complexity, the necessary holistic solutions, the need to respond to changing circumstances, and the high degree of uncertainty necessitate that appropriate policy is developed to meet the challenges.

The study further indicates a difference on the attitude of rural and urban residents toward environmental noise has not change even the awareness of effects on health. This finding is in line with the opinion of Vivienue (2014) on the attitude of high school towards environmental sanitation, an individual who has a positive attitude towards the environment tends to act positively, approaches, show concern, support, and assist the environment but an individual whose attitude is negative towards the environment tends to be indifferent to it or alternate, criticize or even damage it.

The study shows that the residents faced challenges associated with environmental noise. In fact there was an apparent inadequacy of detailed information; most of the respondents indicated that although there was information available about the environmental noise, the level of details and depth did not reach a threshold that could catalyze interest and active participation. Their attitude varies; the attitudes of the residents' towards environmental noise coupled with weak institutional facilities have affected their attitude, beliefs, and behaviour toward environmental noise. This is why Kopnina (2017) argues that to achieve sustainability, business, public, and government stakeholders need to better understand the mechanisms underlying unsustainable practices. So without understanding the mechanism as established by the study then government efforts towards achieving sustainable green environment will be jeopardized. This links with the objective of the study which attempts to assess the perception about challenges associated with environmental noise.

The finding of the study shows that environmental noise cannot be separated from sustainable green environment; this further determines that environmental noise control is crucial to sustainable green environment. It indicates, that environmental noise has a relationship with all the sustainable development, it further demonstrates that noise control is fundamental to sustainable development; it is clear that failure to address environmental noise in a serious and concerted way would present a significant challenge to the realization of the sustainable green environment and will eventually act as a negative restriction on achieving sustainable progress.

Conclusion

Environmental noise has become globally accepted as problems ravaging both developed and developing countries with serious health impacts on human and animals. The degradation of environment will aid the burden of disease by worsening the effects of other adverse factors in the rural and urban environment. The study has examined challenges associated with environmental noise in rural and urban communities in Lagos and solution towards attaining sustainable green environment. While pointing out the perception on challenges associated with environmental noise in rural and urban communities in Lagos, is statistically significant, the paper went further to survey the step which these challenges should be tackled to facilitate attaining sustainable green environment. With the result arising from the findings of this study, the conclusion drawn is that variations exist in challenge associated with environmental noise; failure to address will have negative impacts on human being. Bearing this in mind, education and total reorientation of the resident will be a strong instrument in addressing this.

There is need for education and reorientation to change people behavior and attitude towards new technology, there impacts and policies should be formulated and implemented for the successful achieving sustainable green environment. There is a need for thoroughly planned and effectively executed program of education.

Conclusively, the environmental noise caused by human activities has responsible and will persist with the adverse effects, as a result building a sustainable green environment will restore and save the planet from total collapse.

Recommendation

A healthy environment is necessary for a healthy life of both fauna and flora. Government should as a matter of urgency embark on innovative educational approaches that will make people to understand, address mitigation and how to adapt to the impacts of environmental noise, that will put society on the road toward sustainable green environment. Education that aims at stimulating, motivating and generating the commitment of the people towards the adoption of habits and life styles that is consistent with the practice of sustainable green environment. Education that will play a pivotal role in raising awareness and sensitivity with actions required to promote sustainable green environment. There should be a reorientation of the current education system so as to serve as key to sustainable green environment. Government to provide an informal education program through the various arms of mass media and an aggressive social policy as strategies for educating and changing the orientation, values and practices of individual that relate to environment. Government should embark on mapping existing policies institution and key stakeholders in the context of challenge and opportunities for delivering on sustainable green environment.

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